

Electrocatalysts for the hydrogen evolution reaction in alkaline and neutral media. A comparative review

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Addresses alkaline water electrolysis, a key technology in the decarbonizing society.
- Classifies the materials reported into groups according to chemical composition.
- Evaluates published data critically allowing readers to form their own judgement.
- Provides a brief theoretical background to the parameters used for a comparison.
- Proposes criteria for a comparison of the materials reported in the literature.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

With interest in renewable energy sources and in the decarbonisation of industry rapidly accelerating, alkaline water electrolysis can now be regarded as a key technology enabling efficient energy conversion and storage. Since an alkaline environment is suitable for a vast range of materials with satisfactory chemical stability under operating conditions, the topic of catalysts for the alkaline route could give rise to confusion in the community. Hence, the focus of this review is on analysing the current situation in the electrocatalysis of the hydrogen evolution reaction in an alkaline and a neutral environment, presenting the main group of materials studied, and discussing their potential to achieve industrial relevance. It addresses the main limitations of common parameters used for evaluating and comparing the catalytic activity and stability of selected catalysts. Furthermore, the review provides a comprehensive comparison of catalyst activities with respect to the individual groups depending on their composition as well as to the most used cations and cation-based materials. For the sake of clarity, the comparison is also presented in graphical form. Finally, based on the literature data, fundamental material characteristics to be evaluated in the development of new catalysts for electrochemical water splitting are proposed.

1. Introduction

At the present time, developed countries are striving to reduce their

dependence on fossil fuels and to increase the share of renewable energy sources (RES) in their energy mix. However, implementing RES might lead to fluctuations and subsequent lack of stability in a power

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distribution network due to their dependence on the time of day or year and actual weather conditions [1,2]. One of the promising ways to avoid such fluctuations is the hydrogen economy scheme. The basic idea consists in utilising the instant surplus of electrical energy production and transforming it into the chemical energy of hydrogen which is then stored. Such hydrogen may, consequently, be (i) converted into useful chemicals, (ii) converted back into electrical energy to meet excess demands or (iii) used as a fuel [1].

Currently, the most economic and widespread technologies for the production of hydrogen as a raw material, mainly for the chemical and petrochemical industries, are steam reforming of natural gas, the partial oxidation of hydrocarbons, and coal gasification. As these technologies do not use electrical energy for hydrogen production, they do not represent a viable option for the conversion and storage of energy originating from intermittent RES. Moreover, all the technologies listed depend on fossil fuels and emit CO₂ [3]. An alternative technology for hydrogen production is water electrolysis. It utilises electric power to split the bond between hydrogen and oxygen in a water molecule. It is, therefore, a natural option for energy conversion technology. The CO₂ footprint of water electrolysis is directly related to the source of electrical energy used to power it. Therefore, in combination with RES, it offers a clean alternative to the above-mentioned technologies. Currently three principal versions of the water electrolysis process exist. They are distinguished according to the operating temperature and the nature of the ion transporting charge through the electrolyte [4]:

- High-temperature solid oxide steam electrolysis – due to the high operating temperature, it offers high efficiency without any need for platinum group metal catalysts. However, this is at the expense of the construction material requirements. This is by far the least developed technology of all three groups listed here [5].
- Proton-exchange membrane (PEM) electrolysis - is a highly flexible, intensive and compact technology. On the other hand, the necessity to use Pt-based catalysts significantly increases the related capital expenses [6].
- Alkaline water electrolysis (AWE) - an industrially well-established technology, the drawbacks being that the efficiency, intensity and flexibility are significantly lower than those of the PEM process. One important advantage, however, is its ability to avoid the use of platinum group metals [7].

The last-mentioned option, i.e. the possibility to operate AWE without using precious-metal catalysts for both the hydrogen (HER) and the oxygen (OER) evolution reaction makes it a highly attractive option in the hydrogen economy scheme [7]. To fully exploit its potential, however, the characteristics of AWE technology need to be improved if it is to be competitive with PEM water technology regarding all operational parameters, while maintaining its independence from platinum group metals (PGM). This target opens up several research fields, ranging from general cell construction through to the electrode reactions of catalyst materials and construction of the corresponding catalyst layers.

A zero-gap alkaline electrolyser with an anion-selective membrane is a recent new attractive approach to solve this challenge from a cell construction point of view. In such an arrangement, both electrodes are in direct contact with the membrane, thus minimising the IR drop across the cell [7,8]. In an ideal case, it could also pave the way to utilising demineralised water as a circulating medium in the cell instead of KOH solution. Such an arrangement naturally increases the efficiency and flexibility of the AWE process. At the same time, however, this approach imposes new requirements on the electrode catalysts. This concerns their interaction with polymer electrolytes and their sensitivity to a variation of the pH of the circulating medium. This is the reason why a number of research groups is focusing on the research and development of inexpensive electrocatalysts for the HER. This is documented by the fact that a Web of Science analysis based on the keywords “catalyst,

HER, alkaline NOT acidic” showed an increasing number of publications over the last ten years (from 4 publications in 2010 to 573 in 2020). This immense interest proved to lead to the development of increasingly more active catalysts.

For industrial applications, the newly-developed catalysts have to be highly catalytically active and at the same time long-term stable under intermittent polarisation in an alkaline environment [9]. Hitherto, no clear winner or generally accepted standard has been established for this purpose yet. In the meantime, abundant literature on the topic describes the broad range of materials under study. However, the great variation of testing protocols, which are often not compatible and not directly relevant to the future use of catalysts, makes the current situation in HER catalysis less and less transparent. The focus of this review is to analyse the current situation in electrocatalysis of the HER in an alkaline environment, to present the main group of materials studied and to discuss their potential for reaching the targets required by industry.

2. Hydrogen evolution reaction

The generally accepted mechanism of the HER in alkaline media and neutral media consists of three elementary reaction steps [10–15]:

The Volmer step (1) describes the splitting of a water molecule and adsorption of hydrogen on a free site of the electrode/catalyst surface. This is then followed by hydrogen production via an electrochemical process (Heyrovsky step (2)) and/or chemical process (Tafel step (3)). Several authors have reported that, at low overpotentials, the HER mechanism consists of the Volmer step followed by a parallel Heyrovsky and Tafel step, while at high overpotentials the Tafel step is negligible and the reaction proceeds via the Volmer–Heyrovsky mechanism [16–19].

The electrocatalyst activity towards the HER is strongly influenced by the strength of the Me–H bond [20]. The relation between the HER current density and Me–H bond strength can be expressed by a “volcano” plot. Fig. 1 illustrates the case of pure metals.

Fig. 1 clearly demonstrates that, of all pure metals, noble metals exhibit the highest HER performance. These metals possess hydrogen binding energy close to optimum, allowing the thermodynamically easiest transition from reactants through intermediates to products [10].

Fig. 1. Volcano-type dependence between the exchange current density and Me–H bond strength. Data taken from Ref. [20].

The elements on the left side exhibit weaker Me–H bonds, which limits the adsorption of H atoms on the free catalytic site of the electrode. On the other hand, a strong Me–H bond prevents the creation of a H–H bond and subsequent desorption of produced H_2 [16]. However, it has been proven that the volcano shape given by Sabatier's principle does not always accurately describe the real dependence of HER current density on Me–H bond strength [21]. This is especially true for the materials on the descending (right side) branch of the Volcano plot, as, under conditions corresponding to the studied reaction, they are typically covered by an oxidic layer. Hydrogen atoms are thus not primarily in contact with the metallic state atoms, but with these oxides. This fact was not considered when the first HER Volcano plots were presented. The oxide film can significantly reduce the reaction rate, and thus shift the materials studied to the descending branch [21,22]. Once the oxide-forming metals have been omitted, it is almost possible to obtain linear dependence.

Moreover, at this juncture it is important to stress that the Volcano plot shown in Fig. 1 only considers the energy of hydride formation. However, other key factors influencing the catalytic activity are the position of the *d*-band centre and the specifics of its interaction with hydrogen [21,23]. The *d*-band centre plays an important role regarding the ability of the surface to adsorb other species. The shift of the *d*-band centre with respect to the Fermi level suggests a variation of the adsorption energy. The higher the upward shift, the stronger the binding energy between the metal and the adsorbate can be expected. The great advantage of the *d*-band model is that the position of the *d*-band centre cannot only be measured experimentally, it can also be obtained by density functional calculations (more details in the following paragraphs). This enables the resulting properties of the chosen materials to be predicted [24–26].

The second factor influencing the catalytic activity is the fact that two different states of adsorbed hydrogen can be distinguished [11,21,27]: (i) H_{upd} (underpotential deposition, strongly adsorbed state) and (ii) H_{opd} (overpotential deposition, weakly adsorbed state), the latter being the more reactive state. It has been proven that both states can, to some extent, be adsorbed simultaneously, depending on the current coverage by the H_{upd} [28]. Since the calculated bond strength in Volcano plots corresponds to H_{upd} , it is rather difficult to determine precise values of the hydrogen adsorption energy as the reaction could simply proceed through the intermediate with the more favourable energy from the available options [21,22]. Additionally, unlike in an acid environment where only H^+ can be adsorbed on the active sites, the kinetics in alkaline media may also be affected by the adsorption of OH^- ions. OH_{ad} block the active sites otherwise used for H_2 adsorption, and/or change the energetic states of already adsorbed H atoms (e.g. change of reactive H_{opd} into less reactive H_{upd}), resulting in a higher HER overpotential in alkaline media [11].

From the above, it can be concluded that the Volcano plot attempts to provide a theoretical comparison of pure metals using only a single descriptor (Me–H bond strength). Since there are other factors influencing the overall activity, such a comparison can be considered to be mainly informative. Furthermore, the not entirely clear situation of the oxide-forming metals raises additional questions. In reality, the situation is significantly more complex. The rather general comparison in the form of the Volcano plot becomes insufficient, since alloys, complex compounds, as well as surface modified electrocatalysts represent a practically endless number of options allowing very fine tuning of the bonding energy and electron structure. It is, therefore, important to rationalise research towards optimising the electrocatalyst material in order to save time and resources.

Density functional theory (DFT) has emerged as an attractive tool to provide theoretical insights about the nature of a heterogeneous electrochemical reaction from the point of view of the catalysis/adsorption reaction system [29]. It can be helpful to study each step of a chemical reaction, to find the pathway and mechanism, and eventually the rate-determining step of a studied reaction [30]. Since it is not in the

scope of this review to deal with the DFT approach in its full complexity [31], only the practical applications and major limitations will be briefly addressed in the following paragraphs.

With reference to HER catalysis, DFT calculations are often used to investigate the electronic structure and physical properties of materials studied in order to predict their optimum characteristics (e.g., surface energy, hydrogen binding/adsorption energy, position of *d*-band centre or electron density) [32–34]. Consequently, the most promising candidate of these characteristics is then selected for further experimental examination. If sufficient computing power is available, such a method allows a wide range of materials to be tested relatively simply, fast and inexpensively.

In general, two main approaches regarding the combination of DFT calculations and experimental methods can be distinguished. In the first approach, the DFT calculations support the experimental results obtained and explain the possible reasons for the enhanced catalytic activity of a material [35–38]. To provide an example, according to DFT calculations, the experimentally determined high catalytic activity of the amorphous Co–Mo–P catalyst can be ascribed to the introduction of Mo into the Co–P structure. It influenced the energetics of water dissociation and proton adsorption [35]. In the second approach, DFT calculations can be used to predict a catalyst's performance and suggest the "optimum" structure/composition based on doping the various metals, surface modification, etc. Consequently, such optimised material is synthesised and tested experimentally [34,39]. Yet again to provide an example, the theoretical research on the Pt–Co(OH)₂ catalyst showed better hydrogen adsorption energy than pure Pt. The subsequent experimental results confirmed the theory; the synthesised Pt–Co(OH)₂ catalyst showed better catalytic activity than the commercial Pt/C catalyst.

The major limitations regarding the accuracy of DFT can be associated with the required approximations and selection of functionals (mathematical descriptions of electron density) [40]. Such inaccuracies can lead to serious errors, such as the underestimation of chemical reaction barriers and band gaps of materials, or dissociating and charge transfer excitation energies [41]. Furthermore, even though DFT calculations have recently been providing even more accurate energy-related values, the electron densities are becoming less and less accurate [42]. The probable reason is that the use of more modern functionals leads to unphysical values of electron densities, while maintaining accurate energy-related results. On the other hand, for applications in which the energies are the most important parameters, such calculations might prove to be adequate. Despite this, DFT has become an important tool for optimising the composition of electrocatalysts for different desired electrode reactions.

3. Parameters used to evaluate and compare the catalytic activity of selected materials

In order to compare different electrocatalyst materials, it is important to define corresponding testing protocols and quantitative parameters allowing a comparison under more or less identical conditions. Unfortunately, neither a unified testing protocol nor a method of presenting electrocatalyst data have yet been established. Various parameters evaluating and comparing catalytic activities of selected catalysts are provided in the literature, e.g. turnover frequency, mass and specific activity, Faradaic efficiency, Tafel slope and exchange current density, overpotential at given current density, and stability [6,9,43–47]. The most widely used parameters and their limitations are discussed below.

Specific electrocatalytic activity can be expressed as the current at a fixed overpotential normalised by (i) geometrical surface area, (ii) electrochemical surface area (ECSA), (iii) Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) surface area or (iv) catalyst loading (also referred to as mass activity) [43]. The pros and cons of each normalisation method are reported elsewhere [43,48]. Here, the major drawbacks can be briefly summarised as follows. The geometrical or BET surface area does not

accurately correspond to the real electrochemical active surface. In the case of ECSA, the calculated value determined either by cyclic voltammetry (CV) or impedance analysis can differ significantly, leading to a potential error. Moreover, this method can be used for quantitative evaluation for a strictly limited number of materials. Lastly, normalisation by catalyst loading exhibits lesser experimental inaccuracy, but does not allow a direct comparison of catalysts of varying particle sizes, morphology and topography. On the basis of this, the authors conclude that, if any of these methods of surface determination is used, a fair comparison of differently normalised specific activities is, in principle, not possible.

The turnover frequency (TOF) for the HER, on the other hand, is defined as the average number of moles of H₂ evolved per active site and time unit. It quantifies the specific activity of catalytic centres and can be used to compare various materials. The main drawback of this parameter is the determination of the number of active sites on the catalyst surface. Such information can, in a limited number of cases, be obtained from electrochemical measurements, such as ECSA. Here, a significant error can occur if the material consists of more than one element, since more types of heterogeneous active sites may be present [43,48].

The determination of Tafel parameters (e.g., Tafel slope (b) and exchange current density (j₀)) is another approach. Their values are typically obtained by analysing the polarisation curve in the form of a plot of the logarithmic current density (log(j)) versus *i*R-compensated overpotential (η). The overpotential is defined as the difference between the electrode potential under current load (E_j) and the equilibrium potential (E_r). This dependence is an intrinsic property of the selected material, and it represents an important criterion for characterisation of an electrode reaction catalyst [49,50]. In simple terms, it represents the additional energy needed to (i) overcome an activation barrier of an electrode reaction and (ii) ensure that the electrode reaction proceeds at a given rate.

$$\eta = a + b \cdot \log|j|, \text{ where} \quad (4)$$

$$a = \frac{2.303 \cdot RT}{\alpha F} \log(j_0) \quad (5)$$

$$b = \frac{-2.303 \cdot RT}{\alpha F} \quad (6)$$

The Tafel equation for the HER (4) is fitted to the experimental data. It is important to bear in mind, that the Tafel equation is only valid for the case where the extent of the electrode reaction in a reverse direction is negligible, i.e. for sufficiently high overpotentials. On the other hand, it should also be taken into consideration that, at extremely high overpotentials, the mass transport limitations might influence the results obtained. The Tafel slope (b) and exchange current density (j₀) (see Eq. (5)) can be determined from the fitted parameters. The value of the Tafel slope is determined by the rate-determining step and its position in the reaction mechanism. This is an intensive quantity, i.e. its value is independent of the extent of the catalyst surface. On the contrary, high j₀ indicates a facile electron transfer with a low activation energy. This value is extensive and depends on the extent of the catalyst surface. Apparently, an active catalyst should exhibit a small Tafel slope and high j₀ [43]. However, several issues might lead to a misinterpretation of the catalytic activity. The scan rate, at which a potentiodynamic polarisation curve is determined, strongly influences the values obtained for the Tafel slope and j₀. For that reason, potentiostatic curves or polarisation curves recorded at the lowest possible scan rate with the least experimental inaccuracy should be used [48]. However, even then the j₀ determination can be misinterpreted and, in some cases, can lead to high values even for a non-active catalyst with high overpotential for the HER. The error may occur in the extrapolation of the linear part of the polarisation curve in the logarithmic plot to the zero overpotential. For that reason, it is recommended to perform the extrapolation over as broad a region of overpotential as possible. At the same time, the danger

of errors increases with increasing extent of extrapolation.

The overpotentials at a fixed current density (e.g. 10, 100, 250 and 300 mA cm⁻²) are widely reported quantitative parameters for determining the activity of newly-developed catalysts [6,9,36,44,45,51,52]. This is an extensive characteristic and its value depends on the amount of catalyst used for the test. As a side note, it is important to consider the effect of the gas bubbles produced as well as the mass transport limitation, especially at high current densities (j > 100 mA cm⁻²). These are typically not included in the calculations of the corresponding overpotentials and might strongly influence the overall resistance of the system studied as well as the distribution of local current density.

Catalyst stability represents a very important complementary parameter in the development of an industrially applicable catalyst, even though it does not exactly reflect the catalytic activity itself. Information on this aspect should be available for materials showing promising properties and being claimed to be candidates for an industrial use. Two types of stability tests are usually reported for cathode catalysts: (i) accelerated CV potential cycling at high scan rates [53–56] and (ii) long-term chronoamperometric (CA) or chronopotentiometric (CP) tests [57–59]. In the case of the accelerated stability test by CV cycling, the number of cycles can reach up to several thousand with an upper potential limit up to 0 V vs RHE. To assess the stability of the material, the change in the polarisation curve characteristics, as well as overpotential at a defined current density pre and post CV cycling is compared; the lower the extent of the changes, the higher the stability of the material is claimed to be. Arguably, such accelerated tests might not provide relevant information regarding the “actual” stability of the materials studied under operating conditions. The primary role of a HER catalyst is to maintain its activity under constant AWE conditions for several thousands of hours [60]. However, the accelerated tests typically last for only several hours at best [48,54,57–59], revealing the catalyst stability for power changes. It is clear, however, that, from an industrial point of view, this time is far too short and additional testing is required prior to application on a larger scale [60]. This value is used by the authors to accommodate the testing of large sets of catalysts with reasonable demands on resources.

Considering future connections with RES, stability under intermittent electrolysis conditions also needs to be evaluated. It has been demonstrated that the cathode potential changes in the anodic direction immediately after the electrolyser is switched off [61,62]. This may significantly affect the durability of an otherwise stable catalyst [63,64]. Regrettably, very few authors include the intermittent stability test in their publications. Therefore, along with CV cycling and chronoamperometric or chronopotentiometric experiments, in future such a stability test should also be included in the testing protocol.

Based on the available data, this review proposes a basic guideline to facilitate the research and development of new electrocatalysts.

3.1. Selection of working, reference and counter-electrodes

To obtain reliable experimental data, the use of a rotating disk working electrode (RDE) is recommended, as it provides a well-defined rate of mass transport and can accurately quantify the kinetics of the reaction under study.

For accurate measurement and control of the applied potential, the choice of reference electrode with a stable and well-defined potential is critical. Of the various possibilities, the best option is to use a commercially available reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE). Alternatively, mercury-based electrodes, such as mercury oxide (Hg/HgO), mercury sulfate (Hg/Hg₂SO₄), or silver sulfate (Ag/Ag₂SO₄), are recommended as reference electrodes. Nevertheless, whatever reference electrode is used, converting the electrode potentials and referencing them to the RHE makes a comparison easier for the reader.

The selection of a counter-electrode represents another important parameter. In general, the ideal counter-electrode should be able to (i) sustain higher currents than the working electrode, (ii) yield

homogeneous electric field at the working electrode, and (iii) be stable under operating conditions to prevent contamination of the working electrode and the electrolyte [65].

3.2. Catalyst conditioning

Prior to the activity measurements, the material studied should reach a reproducible and steady state. The catalyst conditioning is usually performed by CV cycling, or continuous CP or CA tests until a stable response is obtained. The conditions used (e.g., potential window, applied potential/current) strongly depend on the studied material and, thus, should be chosen accordingly.

3.3. Determination of activity parameters

In order to determine the activity parameters, accurate recording of a polarisation curve is critical. As already mentioned, the measurement should be performed at the lowest possible scan rate under inert (Ar, N₂) atmosphere. Prior to the determination of the activity parameters, it is necessary to correct the potential in order to subtract the Ohmic losses between the working and the reference electrode (*iR* correction, (7)) [65].

$$E = E_j - iR \quad (7)$$

Where *E* is the *iR*-corrected potential, *E_j* is the applied potential, *i* is current, and *R* is the resistance determined either by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy or current interruption method [66].

Of all the various activity parameters, overpotential at a fixed current density (10 and 250 mA cm⁻²) and a Tafel slope evaluated from Tafel analysis together with an information of a catalyst loading are considered as the key indicators of catalytic activity and can be used as a comparison criterion. Additional activity parameters, such as exchange current density, mass activity and turnover frequency, can also be determined. However, using such parameters for a direct comparison of catalysts of varying particle sizes, morphology and topography is not straightforward and could result in substantial errors. They are, therefore, not recommended for general comparison.

3.4. Evaluation of catalyst stability

Even though it has been generally accepted that it is sufficient to measure the long-term stability of the catalyst for approx. 12 h [43], it is strongly recommended to continue the measurements for at least 240 h to obtain stability results that are at least partly industrially relevant. Additionally, to emulate the connection with RES, short power interruptions/power reductions within an order of minutes should be included in the long-term measurements. Such a procedure will be able to reveal the durability of the material for intermittent water electrolysis.

It follows from the above that a reliable and quantitative catalyst comparison is rather difficult due to the absence of a uniform test protocol. For the purpose of this work, overpotential at a fixed current density (10 mA cm⁻²), Tafel slope, along with at least one of the classical stability tests were chosen as the main comparative parameters. This is due to the fact that they are most widely reported in the literature. Moreover, they can also, to some extent, be used for a direct comparison of individual catalysts if similar experimental conditions are applied (for more details see chapter 5. Comparison of electrocatalysts). The rare publications in which the intermittent stability test has been provided by the authors, will be discussed wherever relevant. In addition, unless otherwise stated, the presented current densities are considered to be cathodic.

4. Overview of electrocatalysts

Due to the great variety of materials studied as potential electrocatalysts for the HER in an AWE process, it is important to set up a clear strategy for their presentation and comparison. Here, the approach used is to present materials in two main groups, i.e. (i) those containing precious metals and (ii) precious metal-free materials. Each was further subdivided into pure metals, alloys and more complex components. Potential research targeting the catalyst stability under different alkalinity of the environment will be discussed in the individual subchapters wherever relevant. This allows a relatively simple analysis of the approaches chosen by different authors.

4.1. Precious metal catalysts

4.1.1. Pure precious metals

Platinum-group metals (PGM), being the most active materials towards the HER, can be considered as a benchmark of cathode catalysts over a broad pH range [4,9,67]. The low-index single crystal facets of Pt play an important role regarding activity toward the HER; the activity trend being (111) < (100) < (110). The reason for such a phenomenon can be explained by the presence of reactive H_{opd} that is most prevalent on the (110) surface [68]. Therefore, the activity of the Pt(110) surface could be an order of magnitude higher than that of the other two surfaces [69].

Although noble metals show the best catalytic activity for the HER, their high price and scarcity make them unsuitable for larger industrial applications [16]. Therefore, optimising the geometric factors of Pt-based catalysts while maintaining electrocatalytic activity has been studied extensively [70–73].

Supporting platinum nanoparticles on a high surface carbon is an inexpensive and easy method to prepare active electrocatalysts. Commercially, the most commonly used 20 wt% Pt deposited on carbon black (Pt/C) is able to achieve one of the lowest values of overpotential of approx. 46 mV at 10 mA cm⁻² under alkaline and also neutral conditions [74–84]. The Tafel slope is significantly dependent on the electrolyte alkalinity (180, 94 and 30 mV dec⁻¹ for 0.01, 0.1 and 1 M KOH, respectively) [85]. Nevertheless, due to their high activity, the Pt/C catalyst is still commonly used as a comparative material for newly-developed catalysts [78,79,86–88]. Ni–Fe layered double hydroxide (Ni–Fe LDH) support matrix with high crystallinity represents another possibility to tether and support Pt nanoparticles [89]. The Ni–Fe LDH–Pt–ht catalyst exhibited overpotential of approx. 101 mV at 10 mA cm⁻² which was 20 mV less than 20 wt% Pt/C catalyst tested under the same conditions.

The second approach to reduce the use of precious metals is the atomic layer deposition (ALD) technique which enables the preparation of Pt nanoparticles, nanoclusters and monolayers of a precisely controlled size [70–72,90,91]. This technique can lead to significantly lower amounts of noble metals (up to 1/10th of a standard Pt loading of approx. 300 μg cm⁻²) [92]. The ALD method has already been successfully utilised to prepare a catalyst monolayer for alkaline fuel cells [92,93]. The optimised 1.08 wt% Pt/N–Mo₂C electrode exhibited a Tafel slope of 108 mV dec⁻¹ and overpotential at 10 mA cm⁻² of 100 mV, which corresponds to approximately 15 times better mass activity of Pt in alkaline media than the commercial 20 wt% Pt/C catalyst [88]. However, the N–Mo₂C support itself exhibits remarkable catalytic activity for the HER [79]. Hence, it is not entirely clear what, in this case, affects the electrode catalytic activity more: the ALD method or the active support.

Even though the reduction of Pt particle size to nano-size is a promising method to reduce Pt loadings, it has proved to reach its limits. Due to the high surface energy, nanosized Pt particles tend to agglomerate or leach out during the electrochemical reaction which leads to a reduction in the active surface of the catalyst [94]. Isolating single Pt atoms in a conductive matrix proved able to minimise this issue. Such an

approach has been successfully applied in various electrochemical processes, such as fuel cell technologies [95], diesel oxidation [96], organic electrosynthesis [97,98] or water electrolysis [44,99,100]. The principle of this technique lies in trapping the individual Pt atoms in the vacancies in the matrix of various supports (e.g. C vacancies in graphene, N vacancies in nitrides, etc.) [99]. For the AWE application, Pt atoms immobilised on a NiRu hydroxide layer (Pt/NiRu–OH) exhibited remarkable activity (overpotential of 38 mV at 10 mA cm^{-2}) [99]. The functionalised NiRu–OH was converted from NiRu layered double hydroxide by Ru leaching and self-reconstruction under OER conditions. Consequently, the NiRu–OH was able to further accelerate water disassociation, while the vacancies originating from the Ru dissolution succeeded in immobilising single Pt atoms.

4.1.2. Precious metal-based alloys

A second approach to reduce precious metal loadings is alloying it with less expensive metals [51,74,101]. A preferable technique is to use one or more metals which have an additional positive effect on the catalytic activity of the material. Scofield et al. [102] prepared a number of crystalline ultrathin Pt–M ($M = \text{Fe, Co, Ru, Cu, Au}$) alloy nanowires in order to partially replace Pt with less expensive metals with favourable synergy. They reported two main reasons for the enhanced performance of the above materials compared with commercial Pt nanoparticle-based catalysts. The first reason is a “ligand effect” which refers to a modification of the electronic properties of the active sites of one transition metal by introducing another metal [103]. The second, a “lattice strain effect”, influences the surface Pt–Pt bond distance caused by incorporating other metals leading to the changes in the d -band centre of Pt [104].

The importance of the position of the metal d -band centre was discussed above. This factor can be altered by incorporating other metals into the lattice, which allows fine-tuning of the catalyst properties [23, 25,26]. These findings are confirmed by the work of Santos et al. [51] and Stojic et al. [105]. Both groups tested various types of Pt-based alloys containing a rare earth metal or molybdenum, respectively. They found out that these alloys exhibit superior activities compared to the individual metals, specifically Pt–Sm and MoPt₂. The latter material exhibited a Tafel slope of 39 mV dec^{-1} and overpotential at 100 mA cm^{-2} of 210 mV. Furthermore, the addition of an ionic activator (Na-molybdate and tris(ethylenediamine)Co(III) chloride) increased the catalytic activity of MoPt₂ even more (Tafel slope of 34 mV dec^{-1} and overpotential at 100 mA cm^{-2} of 196 mV) [106]. In another study, Malik et al. [101], for the first time, utilised the intrinsic magnetic properties of CoPt nanoparticles to improve the stability of the CoPt@Co(OH)₂ catalyst to prolonged exposure (up to 5 days) to the electrolyte. The external magnetic support (neodymium super magnet wrapped with the carbon cloth (CC)) was able to hold the CoPt nanoparticles on the CC

substrate, thus preventing their leaching into the electrolyte solution. This study opens up new opportunities to enhance stability of selected catalysts with similar magnetic properties.

Another interesting finding is the importance of the atomic distribution and segregation throughout the catalyst structure [74,82, 107–109]. Zhang et al. [74] compared plane Pt–Ni alloy and Pt–Ni heterostructure (Fig. 2) with respect to the HER activity. To obtain a current density of 10 mA cm^{-2} , overpotentials of 48, 82 and 61 mV were required for the Pt–Ni heterostructure, Pt–Ni alloy and commercial Pt–C, respectively. The reason for the enhanced activity for the Pt–Ni heterostructure can be attributed to the reduced energy barriers of both water dissociation and H₂ generation caused by atomic segregation of Pt and Ni [74,108].

As follows from the studies focusing on the reduction of precious metal loadings on the AWE cell electrodes, the possibilities of this approach are only limited. Despite this fact, it was possible to achieve a loading reduction by one order of magnitude, while maintaining the cell performance [92]. Nevertheless, the high cost and scarcity of precious metals are still the major obstacles to mass expansion in industry. It should also be noted that many other more critical industrial applications than AWE need to use precious metals [44,45]. It is, therefore, possible to conclude that the most promising approach, especially for large-scale application, is the development of a catalyst based on different, inexpensive materials, where the loading is not a crucial issue with respect to the capital expenses of the final unit.

4.2. PGM-free metals and their alloys

As concluded in the previous chapter, non-precious metal-based catalysts represent the only viable option for the future development of large-scale AWEs for energy conversion purposes. So far, materials based on transition metal-based alloys, sulphides, selenides, phosphides, etc. have been investigated in this respect [6,43–45,110–113]. The next paragraphs summarise selected state-of-the-art cathode electrocatalysts based on the most common transition metal groups and present a direct comparison of the individual groups and Pt-based electrocatalysts.

4.2.1. Fe and Fe-based alloys

Fe is an inexpensive metal widely used in industrial practice. At the same time, it exhibits relatively high HER activity (overpotential can reach the lowest values around 260 mV at 10 mA cm^{-2}) [114,115]. Pure Fe is occasionally used as a comparative material where it can exhibit diverse results with respect to various preparation methods, morphology or surface area [44,116,117]. Regrettably, very little data on pure Fe as a cathode material are available. One possible reason is that Fe alone exhibits worse stability in an alkaline environment at elevated temperature (especially in a currentless state during electrolyser shutdown)

Fig. 2. Scheme of the Pt–Ni alloy and Pt–Ni heterostructure model catalysts [74]. Republished with permission of Royal Society of Chemistry, from [The OH[−]-driven synthesis of Pt–Ni nanocatalysts with atomic segregation for alkaline hydrogen evolution reaction, Zhang, C., et al., 7(10), 2020]; permission conveyed through Copyright Clearance Center, Inc.

[52,118].

4.2.2. Fe alloys

The issue of the limited stability and activity of the Fe cathode under conditions of AWE can be minimised by alloying it with one or more metals [44]. The type of co-alloyed metal, overall composition and preparation method strongly influence both targeted parameters [52, 119–122].

From a historical point of view, steel materials were frequently used as bifunctional catalysts in overall water splitting, even though their catalytic activity, especially for the HER, was far inferior to the state-of-the-art catalysts [123]. Surface modification seems to be a feasible strategy to substantially increase the activity of steel-based materials [123–128]. Just recently, Kim et al. [125] presented self-activated anodic nanoporous stainless steel prepared firstly by anodization (50 V, 10 min), followed by thermal annealing (650 °C, 1 h, Ar/H₂ mixture). The synthesis procedure increased the real surface area of the electrode, providing abundant exposed active sites and oxygen vacancies. The modified material exhibited an overpotential of 370 mV at 10 mA cm⁻², i.e. almost 100 mV lower compared to pristine stainless steel (466 mV). Moreover, the overpotential was further reduced to 244 mV via self-activation after 10 000 cycles of linear sweep voltammetry due to the generation of a catalytically active metal hydroxide layer on the electrode surface. Even though great progress has been achieved in this field, to the best of our knowledge, the most active steel-based catalysts still need doping with more active species, such as Ni, Mo or P, in order to reach overpotentials of only 80–120 mV higher than that observed for commercial Pt/C catalysts [127–130].

Apart from stainless steel, the most studied Fe-based alloys are Fe–Mo and Fe–Co groups that can either be used as binary alloys or complemented by another metal forming more complex systems. Fe–Mo alloys with high real surface area represent promising materials for the HER [122]. The addition of Mo increases the surface roughness (formation of micro-cracks) that can consequently lead to an increase in surface area and possibly enhanced activity. In the chlorate production process, a cathode based on catalyst containing 40.7 at.% Fe and 59.3 at.% Mo exhibited up to 300 mV lower overvoltage for the HER compared to commercial mild steel [131]. Moreover, the corrosion resistance of deposited Fe–Mo can be improved by incorporating a third metal, thus forming a ternary alloy Fe–Mo–M. Ni represents the most promising choice for the third metal in the alloy [132,133]. The Ni_{41.49}Fe_{23.02}Mo_{35.49} alloy exhibited low overpotential of 82 mV at 200 mA cm⁻² and very good long-term stability even for intermittent electrolysis [133].

A novel microwave-assisted electrochemical deposition was reported to allow the formation of Fe–Co alloys with a high Co content up to the Fe:Co ratio close to unity [120]. The high amount of Co, structural defects under fast deposition and thus increased real surface area resulted in a low onset overpotential (145 mV) and Tafel slope (68 mV dec⁻¹) of the HER, and high exchange current density (20 mA cm⁻²).

Another approach to enhance the activity of Fe-based alloys is the change in their crystalline structure to nano-crystalline or completely amorphous via rapid solidification. An amorphous structure represents a thermodynamically unstable state of the material and is thus characterised by a different oxidation state of the surface atoms compared to the crystalline one. Alloys with an amorphous structure exhibit many attractive properties, such as high corrosion resistance, promising mechanical stability and sufficient electrochemical activity [9,132,134]. Moreover, various researchers have reported that the catalytic activity of certain amorphous alloys can be improved by surface activation [52, 119,135,136]. Müller et al. [52] prepared a series of amorphous Fe₈₂B₁₈, Fe₈₀Si₁₀B₁₀, Fe₆₀Co₂₀Si₁₀B₁₀ alloys and investigated their catalytic activity and stability for the HER in alkaline media. Fe₆₀Co₂₀Si₁₀B₁₀ exhibited the best stability and activity. In the subsequent work [136], the Fe₆₀Co₂₀Si₁₀B₁₀ catalyst combined with an anion-selective binder was tested in a zero-gap membrane electrolyser. The catalyst activated

by chemical leaching in KOH solution achieved superior stability in the electrolyser (more than 240 h of continuous operation) compared to other stability tests cited in the literature [13,55,77,137].

Even though Fe-based alloys generally do not exhibit comparable catalytic activity to the PGM catalyst, their low cost, high abundance and sufficient stability make them suitable for practical applications. Of the above-mentioned materials, the Fe–Mo–Ni alloy with high activity and stability seems to be a promising and interesting catalyst for further optimisation.

4.2.3. Co-based alloys

Co-based catalysts have attracted much attention for their excellent electrical conductivity and durability in alkaline media [13,44]. Co–Mo alloys and their modifications belong to the most investigated Co-based catalysts [138–143]. The content of Mo in Co–Mo alloy strongly influences the catalytic activity and hardness of the material [139]. The Co–Mo catalyst containing 45% of Mo in the alloy exhibited high catalytic activity (Tafel slope of 103 mV dec⁻¹ and high exchange current density of 499·10⁻⁴ mA cm⁻²). The addition of Ni to the binary Co–Mo alloy increased the real surface area, which resulted in enhanced catalytic activity of the ternary Co–Ni–Mo alloys (overpotential of 110 mV at 10 mA cm⁻² compared to 145 mV for the Co–Mo alloy) [64].

A surprising fact regarding Co-based materials emerged after testing them under neutral environment conditions. The hollow nanoparticles of Co nanocrystal (Co–HNP) proved to be an efficient and stable catalyst [144]. The well-designed nanostructure morphology enhanced the specific area, resulting in increased catalytic activity (overpotential of 85 mV at 10 mA cm⁻² in 1 M phosphate buffer saline (PBS), pH 7). Additionally, the catalyst maintained a stable overpotential of approx. 330 mV for 20 h at 150 mA cm⁻².

Apart from alloying with other metals, Co is more commonly used in other compounds (e.g. sulphides and phosphides) where it can provide sufficient activity and stability under different alkalinities of the environment (see corresponding paragraphs).

4.2.4. Ni and Ni-based alloys

Ni alone is one of the most investigated materials for the HER in alkaline media on account of its excellent stability in an alkaline environment and sufficient catalytic activity towards the HER [117]. However, the activity strongly depends on the Ni morphology and surface area [117,145–147]. Ni in the form of foam or mesh exhibited relatively high overpotential of approx. 217 mV and 275 mV at 10 mA cm⁻², respectively [117]. Urchin-like Ni nanoparticles with a high roughness factor exhibited slightly lower overpotential of 180 mV under similar conditions [75]. However, the overpotential of pure Ni starts to increase after a certain time under cathodic polarisation in alkaline media. This can be attributed to the formation of a hydride layer on the active Ni surface [148,149].

A very promising and cost-effective approach to increase the activity and, possibly, even the long-term stability of pure Ni is the addition of reduced graphene oxide (rGO), either by single-step Ni electrodeposition/GO reduction [150,151] or by direct GO reduction on Ni support [152]. In such a case, the rGO enhances the recombination of H adatoms on the catalyst surface, leading to much higher activity of the prepared materials [150–152]. As an example, Gutić et al. [150] reported that the Ni@rGO composite exhibits reduced overpotential of 97 mV at 10 mA cm⁻² (approx. 200 mV lower than pure electrodeposited Ni). However, as the authors claim, their work only addresses the electrocatalytic activity of the catalyst without considering its stability and durability. On the other hand, a different study showed that the rGO electrochemically reduced on Ni foam showed excellent durability (up to 30 days) in a membrane alkaline electrolyser [152]. Nevertheless, as this is a very interesting option, more research regarding the stability of rGO under HER conditions as well as in a current-less state in an alkaline medium is needed.

4.2.5. Ni alloys

Ni can also be used in alloys with different metals, and oxide or non-oxide groups [132,137,149,153–160]. The addition of other metals (such as Co, Mo, Fe) or groups influences various properties of pure Ni, e.g. electronic configuration, $\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{H}_2$ adsorption/desorption, kinetics, etc. [158].

Raney-type electrodes (mainly Ni or Co and Fe doped with Al or Zn) exhibit a high surface area and decent catalytic activity after leaching in alkaline solutions [9]. Herraiz-Cardona et al. [161] prepared high performance Raney-type Ni and Ni–Co porous electrodes by galvanic co-deposition using a graphite counter-electrode. Even though the incorporation of Co increases the intrinsic catalytic activity per unit of true surface area, the overall lower surface roughness caused by the change in surface morphology results in higher overpotential and lower exchange current density. For this reason, additional research regarding the optimisation of the surface area still needs to be conducted. Furthermore, material that the authors call “stainless Raney nickel” (SRN) represents a promising option [162]. SRN coatings can be prepared by replacing a graphite counter-electrode by 316-grade stainless steel (316SS) in the electrodeposition procedure. The use of a sacrificial stainless-steel counter-electrode affected the composition of the finished coatings (co-deposition of Fe, Cr, Mo and Cu). The obtained material exhibited a higher electrochemical surface area and longer lifetime.

Ni–Mo alloys are the benchmark of non-platinum catalysts [80, 163–165]. The reason for their high activity is claimed to be the synergistic effect between adjacent atoms of Ni and Mo, resulting in unsaturated d-orbits similar to Pt [80]. Raj et al. extensively studied

electrodeposited Ni-based alloys and found that binary and ternary alloys containing Mo are the most active materials for the HER [156,166, 167]. Moreover, the post-deposition reductive annealing or addition of carbon black can significantly increase the HER activity of Ni–Mo catalysts [165]. On the other hand, the activity decreases at a positive potential due to the dissolution of Mo oxides [63]. This could be a problem, especially during intermittent operation of industrial electrolysers (the cathode potential changes in the anodic direction immediately after the electrolyser is disconnected from the power source) [61, 62].

The Raney-type Ni–Mo alloys fabricated by atmospheric plasma spraying of NiAlMo powder on nickel sheet showed interesting properties for the HER [168]. After part of the Al had been leached out during the activation in KOH, the electrode exhibited low overpotential of 82 mV at 200 mA cm^{-2} and a Tafel slope of 36 mV dec^{-1} .

According to the available reported data, one of the most active materials for the HER is MoNi_4 supported by MoO_2 cuboids on Ni foam [164]. Its specific surface morphology and synthesis procedure played a major role in the catalytic activity of the material. The synthesis of $\text{MoNi}_4/\text{MoO}_2/\text{Ni}$ involves two steps (Fig. 3). In the first step, the NiMoO_4 cuboids were grown on nickel foam via a hydrothermal reaction (150°C , 6 h, solution containing $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $(\text{NH}_4)_6\text{Mo}_7\text{O}_{24} \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$). In the following step, the precursors were calcined in H_2/Ar atmosphere (500°C , 2h). During the calcination, the inner Ni atoms diffused outwards, forming MoNi_4 nanoparticles directly on the surface of the MoO_2 cuboids. As a result, the $\text{MoNi}_4/\text{MoO}_2/\text{Ni}$ catalyst exhibited remarkably low overpotential of 15 mV at 10 mA

Fig. 3. Synthesis scheme of $\text{MoNi}_4/\text{MoO}_2/\text{Ni}$ catalyst [164].

cm^{-2} and a Tafel slope of 30 mV dec^{-1} . Moreover, the stability test (30 h) proved this material to be fairly stable under alkaline water electrolysis conditions (increase of 3, 2 and $5 \text{ mV}/10 \text{ h}$ at 10, 100 and 200 mA cm^{-2} , respectively). Nevertheless, the stability of the catalyst during intermittent operation remains another question.

The application of nickel-molybdenum coatings on hydrogen storage alloys (MmNi_{3.6}Co_{0.75}Mn_{0.4}Al_{0.27} (Mm = misch metal), LaNiSi and Ti₂Ni) can significantly improve the endurance of Ni–Mo species to intermittent electrolysis [63,153,169,170]. Whilst the Ni–Mo coating works as the HER catalyst, the hydrogen storage alloys enhance the corrosion resistance by the absorption of hydrogen during electrolysis and subsequent desorption during shutdowns and maintenance [9,63]. Recently, Madram et al. [171] synthesised a ternary Ni–P–La hydrogen storage alloy on a copper substrate by co-electrodeposition with excellent long-term stability (2000 h) and high activity (Tafel slope of 93 mV dec^{-1} and overpotential of 139 mV at 250 mA cm^{-2}).

Besides in an alkaline environment, Ni-based materials have also proven to be applicable in a neutral environment [84,172,173]. A nitrogen-modified porous Ni framework exhibited remarkable catalytic activity (overpotential of 64 mV at 10 mA cm^{-2}) as well as robust stability (18 h, 20 mA cm^{-2} , pH 7) under HER conditions [84]. To the best of our knowledge, such activity in a neutral environment is one of the best of the non-precious materials yet reported and can even bear comparison with the commercial Pt/C catalyst (overpotential of approx. 46 mV at 10 mA cm^{-2}).

As demonstrated, the activity of pure Ni in alkaline media is not yet comparable to that of the PGM catalyst. Instead, Ni in the form of foam or mesh can serve as an excellent support due to its high electric conductivity, surface area and stability, as well as sufficient activity. On the other hand, the combination of Ni and Mo proved to be a promising way for developing an active catalyst, even though the stability during intermittent electrolysis in some cases still remains a problem. Furthermore, research into the use of Ni-based materials at neutral pH could also yield extraordinary results and should be pursued in greater depth.

4.3. Other PGM-free material groups

Recently, the combination of transition metals and non-metal elements (S, Se, N, C, P) has emerged as a promising option to replace noble metals [44]. The following chapters will discuss recent progress in the catalytic activity and stability of selected non-alloyed groups (sulphides, selenides, nitrides, carbides and phosphides).

4.3.1. Metal sulphides

Low cost and simple preparation make metal sulphides promising candidates as cathode catalysts [112,174–178]. Moreover, representatives of this group can be used in a full range of pH. Molybdenum sulphide (MoS₂) is one of the most investigated and oldest candidates of the sulphide group [174,179,180]. In acidic media, metallic MoS₂ exhibited decent catalytic activity (Tafel slopes around 42 mV dec^{-1} and overpotential at 10 mA cm^{-2} around 180 mV) [179,181]. Furthermore, incorporation of first row 3d transition metals (e.g., Fe, Co, Ni) and other selected elements can significantly improve the otherwise sluggish activity of MoS₂ in alkaline media [182,183]. Recently, Cao et al. [183] used heteroatom doping (Co, O) and phase transformation of MoS₂ to synthesise the dual-doped metallic octahedral Co₂O–MoS₂ on carbon nanotubes with an overpotential of 113 mV at 10 mA cm^{-2} and a corresponding small Tafel slope of 50 mV dec^{-1} , accompanied by robust stability in alkaline media.

Ni-based sulphides have also been reported as catalysts for the HER under acidic and alkaline conditions [58,178,184,185]. Even though single atom sulphides NiS, NiS₂ and Ni₃S₂ with relatively high overpotential are still far inferior to other similar materials, several possibilities to improve their performance exist [174]. The combination of Ni with other metals or metal-based materials seems to be one of the

promising options [54,109,185–188]. For example, defect-rich hetero-interfaces of MoNi-based sulphides on carbon cloth prepared via a hydrothermal process exhibited low overpotential of 68 mV at 10 mA cm^{-2} . The interface structure could provide sufficient distribution of electrolyte as well as release the gas produced. Furthermore, according to the authors, the synergistic effect and strong interaction between the metals boosted the HER performance [186]. Optimisation of the NiS_x structure also proved to be a successful method to develop a highly active and inexpensive catalyst [189]. The hierarchically macroporous structure of h-NiS_x with a 3D configuration enhanced the catalytic activity for both the HER and the OER. The catalyst achieved a very low overpotential of 60 mV at 10 mA cm^{-2} for the HER. However, even though the structural analysis after the stability test did not reveal any morphological or composition changes, the increase in overpotential by 10 mV during 10 h of electrolysis suggests that some degradation might have occurred [189].

Recently, metal sulphides have also been extensively studied for their possible application at neutral pH [172,190–192]. The combination of Ni and Co sulphides in the form of Ni_{0.33}Co_{0.67}S₂ outperformed both CoS₂ and NiS₂ at neutral pH, reaching a low overpotential of 72 mV at 10 mA cm^{-2} (1 M PBS, pH 7) [173]. For comparison, both single metal-based sulphides exhibited current densities of 6.6 and 3 mA cm^{-2} , respectively, at the same overpotential and under identical conditions.

Although this group of materials represents a fairly conventional approach, there is still enough room for further optimisation or the discovery of novel methods. Surface modification as well as structure and composition optimisation could provide active catalysts for the HER in both a neutral and an alkaline environment. Regarding the activity, the most promising seems to be h-NiS_x. On the other hand, surface treatment could lead to impaired stability under HER conditions due to the reconstruction or deterioration of the modified surface.

4.3.2. Metal selenides

According to the literature available hitherto, transition metal selenides exhibit higher catalytic activity compared to metal sulphides [6, 43,178]. Also in the case of selenides, the activity of the catalyst is strongly influenced by the number of active sites on its surface, as the reaction proceeds exclusively on the crystal edges [193–196]. It is, therefore, necessary to optimise the catalyst surface to provide enriched, active edge sites. For instance, nanostructured defect-rich MoSe₂ with highly exposed active edge sites exhibited significantly lower overpotential than defect-free MoSe₂ (243 mV vs 364 mV at 10 mA cm^{-2}) [193]. Moreover, according to DFT calculations, the defect-rich structure enhanced water dissociation. This probably led to a change in the rate-determining step of the HER mechanism (the Tafel slope decreased from 112 to 68 mV dec^{-1}).

Similar to sulphides, the combination of metal selenides and other metals or metal-based materials has also received a great deal of attention in the past decade [107,195–198]. Fe-doped NiSe nanosheets on Ni foam exhibited high and stable catalytic activity for both the OER and the HER in alkaline solution. For the HER, the catalyst achieved an overpotential of 163 and 296 mV at 10 and 500 mA cm^{-2} , respectively [198]. Surprisingly, the CoSe/MoSe₂ catalyst was stable in the entire range of the electrolyte pH and exhibited better activity in an alkaline environment than in an acidic one (overpotential of 115 mV vs 190 mV at 10 mA cm^{-2}) and a Tafel slope of 54 mV dec^{-1} vs 62 mV dec^{-1} [197]. Recently, self-supported Ni₂P-decorated NiSe₂ nanosheet arrays on carbon cloth have been reported as a very active catalyst for the HER [107]. The novel heterostructure presented facilitated strong electronic interaction between Ni₂P and NiSe₂ and also provided a large number of catalytically active sites. The catalyst maintained a low overpotential of 66 mV to drive a current density of 10 mA cm^{-2} for 12 h without significant degradation.

Overall, the metal selenides follow similar path to the metal sulphides with respect to their ability to provide an active catalyst for the HER in an alkaline medium. Apart from surface modification, the

combination of metal selenide and other group(s) (such as phosphides or sulphides) should be pursued further, as it can also provide a large number of active sites leading to an active catalyst (eg., Ni₂P–NiSe₂). Moreover, metal selenides have also been successfully tested in an acidic environment [199–201]. For this reason, it would also be appropriate to examine these materials under neutral pH conditions as, hitherto, only a limited number of publications focusing on such a topic have been reported so far [202].

4.3.3. Metal nitrides

Transition metal nitrides have recently emerged as efficient HER electrocatalysts due to their unique electronic structure and metal-like electric conductivity [110]. Moreover, the M–N bond affects the position of the metal *d*-band centre, resulting in higher electron donating ability of the corresponding metal nitride [203]. These aspects make metal nitrides very attractive materials for further research.

The conventional method of nitride preparation is direct nitridation. Heating a nickel foam in a NH₃ atmosphere can yield an active Ni₃N/Ni foam catalyst (overpotential of 121 mV at 10 mA cm⁻²) that is also stable in an alkaline environment (1 M KOH, 32 h). It should be noted that a slight degradation could be observed at a higher temperature (60 °C) in a concentrated (>4 M) KOH solution [81]. Additionally, the Ni₃N catalyst in the form of nanosheets prepared by a sintering process shows interesting activity (overpotential of 112 mV at 10 mA cm⁻²) and stability (12 h at 90 mA cm⁻²) even at neutral pH (1 M PBS) [204].

Mo and Co doping can significantly improve the performance of metal nitrides towards the HER [37,78]. The Mo-doped Ni₃FeN anode catalyst exhibited low overpotential of 69 mV at 10 mA cm⁻² for the HER [37]. The nanocomposites of metallic cobalt and molybdenum nitride on a nitrogen-doped carbon matrix (Co–Mo₂N@NC) exhibited an unusual HER performance with an overpotential of 47 mV at 10 mA cm⁻² and a Tafel slope of 43 mV dec⁻¹ [205]. However, even though the authors claim that the catalyst is stable in alkaline media, the durability test graph presented shows a gradual decrease in current density from approx. 10 to 6 mA cm⁻² in 12 h. This observation indicates that degradation might, to some extent, have occurred.

Nitrides can even show a bifunctional character. Yuan et al. [206] designed a highly efficient and stable bifunctional catalyst with cobalt nitride embedded in nitrogen-doped carbon (Co₄N@NC). The catalyst was first synthesised via self-assembly by a mechanical mixing method, followed by the nitridation process. The nitrogen-doped carbon suppressed the surface oxidation of Co₄N in an alkaline medium (Fig. 4) and improved the electric conductivity. The catalyst, therefore, exhibited a

very low overpotential of 62 mV at 10 mA cm⁻² and a Tafel slope of 37 mV dec⁻¹, as well as high stability in an alkaline environment (1 M KOH) without any significant current density decrease for 72 h under a constant potential of –78 mV vs RHE.

Similar to previous groups, elemental doping and surface modification proved to be feasible strategies to design an active nitride-based catalyst. Co- or Mo-containing nitrides are able to achieve Pt-like activity in alkaline media. Moreover, the Co₄N@NC catalyst also exhibited remarkable stability and electric conductivity. Another factor that should be considered is the simplicity of the catalyst preparation with respect to the potential industrial application. A fine-tuned or multi-step method can provide an active catalyst in the laboratory, but such a method might not be applicable on a large scale.

4.3.4. Metal carbides

Similar to nitrides, metal carbides also exhibited Pt-like properties and HER activity due to the shift in the *d*-band centre [82,113,203]. WC is the most commonly studied candidate possessing activity close to Pt in HER electrocatalysis [82,86,207]. However, its stability at anodic potentials is very low due to the formation of a passive WO₃ layer [208]. Therefore, WC is more commonly used as a substrate for a compact Pt monolayer loading where it can deliver a performance comparable to bulk Pt [209], but is at the same time protected from oxidative degradation. The stability of WC without the need of precious metals as well as the HER activity can also be enhanced by Ni doping [210,211] or by changing its structure [82]. In the latter, Chen et al. synthesised a eutectoid WC/WC₂ heterostructure with high catalytic activity (75 mV at 10 mA cm⁻²) and superior stability (over 480 h) in alkaline media. The authors claim that this is the first time for such a eutectoid-structure to be reported as an efficient catalyst for the HER in alkaline solution.

Alternatively, Mo and Co-based carbides were tested for the HER [44,79,163,212]. Mo₂C-embedded nitrogen-doped porous carbon nanosheet (Mo₂C@2D-NPCs) material was able to achieve catalytic activity comparable to commercial Pt-based catalysts (overpotential of 45 mV at 10 mA cm⁻²) [79]. Regarding the stability, the 20-h stability test in 1 M KOH showed a gradual decrease in current density from approx. 24 to 16 mA cm⁻². On another note, a Co–Mo bimetallic carbide catalyst exhibited comparable HER activity (overpotential of 46 mV at 10 mA cm⁻² and Tafel slope of 46 mV dec⁻¹) but much higher stability (500 h of continuous operation without any decline in activity) in alkaline solution [212]. The high catalytic activity of this material is attributed to the introduction of Co atoms into the Mo₂C crystal cells which decreases the content of the less active high valence Mo species and increases the low valence Mo states [79].

Low cost, high abundance and the possibility to achieve superb activity make metal carbides ideal candidates for HER catalysts in alkaline media. Nevertheless, their stability during intermittent operation remains an crucial open question as carbon-based materials are prone to corrosion even under mild oxidative conditions [213–215]. For this reason, future research in this area should focus on stability under anodic polarisation which can occur after the electrolyser is switched off.

Surprisingly, to the best of our knowledge, metal carbides do not exhibit favourable activity toward the HER at neutral pH. The materials reported, such as NiC [84] or Mo₂C [216], demonstrated relatively high overpotentials of 200 and 204 mV at 10 mA cm⁻², respectively. Just recently, self-supported Cu@WC nanowires emerged as a promising catalysts over a broad pH range [217]. In accordance with the theory describing the influence of pH on HER catalytic activity, the Cu@WC nanowires exhibited lowest overpotential in an acidic environment of 92 mV at 10 mA cm⁻² (119 and 173 mV for an alkaline and a neutral environment, respectively). However, the overpotential at neutral pH is still rather high compared to the other groups of materials reported. It would, therefore, be beneficial to further determine the exact reasons for the poor activity of such materials.

Fig. 4. Suppressed oxidation of Co₄N@NC [206]. Reprinted (adapted) with permission from Yuan, W., et al., *Interfacial Engineering of Cobalt Nitrides and Mesoporous Nitrogen-Doped Carbon: Toward Efficient Overall Water-Splitting Activity with Enhanced Charge-Transfer Efficiency*. ACS Energy Letters, 2020: p. 692–700. Copyright (2020) American Chemical Society.

4.3.5. Metal phosphides

Metal phosphides have been considered as potential HER catalyst candidates for several decades [218–221]. One of the reasons is that, apart from metal sulphides and selenides, the activity of phosphides is not limited to the sites of crystal edges, but the HER can proceed in the bulk material, too [6]. Nickel- and cobalt-based phosphides are among the most investigated members of the this group [36,57,59,222–227]. One of many examples, the 3D microporous NiFeCoP/NM electrode prepared by a simple electrodeposition method, exhibited remarkable catalytic activity for the HER and delivered a current density of 10 mA cm⁻² at an extremely low overpotential (33 mV) with a relatively small Tafel slope (71.1 mV dec⁻¹) in 1 M KOH solution.

The catalytic activity of metal-based phosphides can be further enhanced by appropriate doping with other elements. N-doped NiCoP nanowires (NW) on carbon fibre paper (CFP) were synthesised by a hydrothermal reaction followed by a phosphorisation-nitrogenation method [36]. The authors reported that the N dopant preferably replaced O defects rather than P atoms in the lattice. Consequently, the N-NiCoP NWs/CFP exhibited up to 61% better catalytic activity (overpotential of 162.5 mV at 100 mA cm⁻²) as compared to NiCoP NWs/CFP in alkaline media. Furthermore, amorphous Mo-doped Co-P catalyst synthesised by room temperature electrodeposition is one of the most active Pt-free catalyst yet reported [35]. The addition of Mo positively influenced the energetics of water dissociation and M–H binding energy of the material, resulting in an active (overpotential of 30–35 mV at 10 mA cm⁻²) and stable (24 h without increasing overvoltage) cathode catalyst.

Just recently, metal phosphides have yet again attracted much attention due to their interesting properties toward the HER. The Mo-doped Co-P catalyst outperformed the majority of Pt-based catalysts in terms of activity and stability under HER conditions. On the other hand, similar to previous groups, stability under anodic polarisation should continue to be tested. The metal phosphides tend towards surface oxidation under anodic polarisation, forming corresponding oxides/hydroxides [33].

Moreover, a Web of Science analysis using the keywords “phosphide, alkaline, HER” showed that, in 2014, only 2 publications focusing on metal phosphides as an efficient HER catalyst in alkaline media were reported. In 2019, the number of publications totalled more than 170. These records clearly indicate the direction of research today.

Similar to metal sulphides, metal phosphides have also been studied as promising HER catalysts at neutral pH [83,219,228]. Nanostructured FeP deposited on TiO₂ is one of the most active representatives of the phosphide group (overpotential of 102 mV at 10 mA cm⁻² in 1 M PBS). Moreover, the FeP catalyst was also successfully utilised for photocatalytic production in both acidic and neutral pH solutions [83].

4.3.6. Surface hydroxylation of non-oxide/hydroxide materials

An interesting practise widely used in OER catalysis is the surface hydroxylation of non-oxide/hydroxide materials [178,229–231]. Exposing the selected non-precious metal chalcogenides and phosphides to an alkaline and oxidative environment can potentially lead to an anion exchange (formation of corresponding hydroxides), as well as amorphisation of the surface, thus enhancing the overall catalytic activity of the modified materials [177,229,232,233]. However, since the activity of hydroxide-based catalysts for the HER is, in general, unsatisfactory, such a technique has tended to be neglected in HER catalysis [234,235]. Recently, two novel publications utilising anion exchange for HER catalysis have been reported [177,232]. An anodically polarised Ni–S/Ni foam catalyst (Ni–S–OH/Ni foam) exhibited an overpotential of 305 mV at 100 mA cm⁻², which is 110 mV lower compared to pristine Ni–S/Ni foam (415 mV at 100 mA cm⁻²) [177]. A similar trend was observed for CoP nanosheets [232]. The modified Co(OH)_x@CoP catalyst showed high HER activity with an overpotential of 100 mV at 10 mA cm⁻². The improved activity can be attributed to the formation of low valence Co species of Co(OH)_x on the surface of CoP which

enhanced the water dissociation step in the water electrolysis mechanism. As expected, the Co(OH)₂ nanosheets used for purposes of comparison showed poor HER activity, suggesting that the high activity of the Co(OH)_x@CoP catalyst is derived from a strong synergistic effects between Co(OH)_x and CoP. These recent findings open up a promising way to further enhance the activity of non-oxide-based materials towards the HER. Future developments in this field of research would also benefit from verification of the use of this experimental technique which could even be used for other materials, such as selenides, nitrides and carbides.

5. Comparison of electrocatalysts

A direct comparison of various catalysts for the HER in alkaline media is a challenging task. As already mentioned, the main reason is the absence of standard testing protocols, as each author group tests the materials under different conditions (electrolyte solution, temperature, catalyst support, electrode potential scan rates, etc.). In this review, the authors attempted to gather sufficient data describing the catalytic activity of various cathode catalysts in an alkaline environment, e.g. overpotential at specified current densities, onset overpotential and Tafel slopes. A table containing the numerical values of the parameters reported for all the selected materials compared in this chapter using a graphical form can be found in the Supporting Information (Table S1). In addition, for the sake of clarity, box plots were chosen to illustrate the direct comparison of the individual groups as well as of the most commonly used cations and cation-based materials. In general, the box plot shows the 25th and 75th percentile, median, average, error bars (showing 10th and 90th percentile) and outlying points. Overpotential at 10 mA cm⁻², which is the most frequently reported value for the majority of materials, was selected as a comparative criterion on the y axis. The reason for choosing such a value is that the current density of 10 mA cm⁻² is expected to be relevant for integrated solar water-splitting devices [236]. For this reason, unless otherwise stated, all overpotentials mentioned in the following paragraphs are reported for a current density of 10 mA cm⁻².

5.1. Comparison of cations

Fig. 5 shows the comparison of the activity of only a single metal (SM) based material (e.g. Ni₂P, Fe₈B₁₈, Co nanoparticles, MoC₂ ...). As can be seen from the graph, Pt-free SM-based materials are not ideal as cathode catalysts due to the higher overpotential needed to drive a current density of 10 mA cm⁻². However, some of the SM materials

Fig. 5. Comparison of overpotentials at 10 mA cm⁻² achieved by single metal-based cathode catalysts in alkaline media. 1 – outlying values, 2 – 90th percentile, 3 – 75th percentile, 4 – mean value, 5 – median, 6 – 25th percentile, 7 – 10th percentile.

display values comparable to Pt-based catalysts. For Co and Ni metals, the most active materials are based on phosphides (CoP/CC 48 mV [237], CoP-MNA/Ni foam 54 mV [238] and Ni₅P₄ 49 mV [239]). The situation is different for Mo-based materials. The most promising catalysts are based on a carbide group; the most active material is Mo₂C-embedded N-doped porous carbon nanosheets (see paragraph 4.3.4 Metal carbides). Choosing between Co-, Ni- or Mo-based non-precious SM catalysts, Ni being the cheapest and the most abundant seems to be the most promising choice. It should be noted that no satisfactory data regarding SM-based catalysts are available (especially for Fe). Typically, these materials are combined with other metals which significantly improve their catalytic activity.

As stated above, the combination of SM-based materials can substantially improve their catalytic activity (Fig. 6). The average overpotential decreases by approximately 100, 20, 42 and 45 mV for Fe-, Co-, Ni- and Mo-based materials, respectively. The overpotential of the majority of Pt-free catalysts ranges between 90 and 240 mV (45–90 mV for Pt-based materials). Despite the fact that, in general, PGM-based catalysts still exhibit superior activity compared to other non-precious materials, they cannot be considered for future mass application in alkaline water electrolyzers (see chapter 4.1 Precious metal catalysts).

A surprising fact regarding the activity of Pt-free materials is that there is not a significant difference in the types of metal used. According to the literature, it is possible to achieve overpotentials comparable to Pt-based catalysts with every metal-based group. Generally, the most active materials consist of Ni or Co metals doped with Fe or Mo in the form of alloys (Ni₄Mo [165], NiMo NWS/Ni foam [163]) or complemented by a phosphide group (Mo–CoP [35], NiFeCoP [111]).

Another interesting observation is that the combination of SM-based materials alone may not always lead to more active catalysts (compare high outlying points for Pt and Co-based materials in Figs. 5 and 6). The reason for this inferior activity can be explained by the different morphology of the materials (e.g. crystallinity or number of active sites), which can, however, be further optimised [64,240]. In the case of Pt-based material, Pt deposited on optimised WS₂ with rich exposed edges exhibited much higher catalytic activity (overpotential of 49 mV) than edge-poor WS₂ (overpotential of 195 mV) [240]. For the Co-based material, the sluggish activity of Co–Ni alloy (overpotential of 550 mV) was enhanced by the addition of Mo. The resulting nanocrystalline Co–Ni–Mo alloy exhibited significantly higher surface roughness along with higher activity (overpotential of 110 mV) [64].

Fig. 6. Comparison of overpotentials at 10 mA cm⁻² achieved by metal-based cathode catalysts in alkaline media. 1 – outlying values, 2 – 90th percentile, 3 – 75th percentile, 4 – mean value, 5 – median, 6 – 25th percentile, 7 – 10th percentile.

5.2. Comparison of individual groups

Fig. 7 shows the comparison of the most common individual material groups. Each box comprises all materials which at least partly contain the group named (e.g. Ni₂P–NiSe₂ would be included in both phosphide and selenide groups).

In general, the Pt-based catalyst still ranks among the most active catalysts, though having the lowest overpotential (e.g. 17 and 32 mV for Ru@C₂N [73] and Pt–Co(OH)₂/CC [74], respectively). By comparing mean values and medians, catalysts containing phosphorous-based groups get closest to materials based on precious metals. Surprisingly, Pt-free alloys, even though not the most active materials overall, can achieve superb catalytic activity even comparable to the best Pt-based catalysts (see lower outlying points in Fig. 7) [44,164]. Of those groups, the most promising materials are Ni₄Mo (15 mV) [165], NiMo NWS/Ni foam (30 mV) [163], as well as Mo–CoP (30 mV) [35]. These results suggest that molybdenum doping is a prospective method to obtain active materials for the HER. On the other hand, catalytic activity is only one of the parameters needed to be considered. As already discussed for Ni–Mo alloys (paragraph 4.2.3 Ni and Ni-based alloys), the stability of Mo present in such materials becomes an issue, especially during intermittent operation of industrial electrolyzers [61,62]. The positive shift in electrode potential immediately after a device is turned off could lead to the oxidation of Mo-species [63]. For this reason, new stability tests taking intermittent electrolysis into account should also be included in the testing protocols for all newly developed catalysts.

5.3. Activity in neutral vs alkaline environment

The comparison of the catalytic activity of selected materials in alkaline and neutral media is summarised in Fig. 8. As expected, the best performance in both environments is achieved by Pt-based materials. However, some candidates, such as modified Ni, Co and their corresponding sulphides and phosphides, have emerged as active materials even at neutral pH. A nitrogen-modified porous Ni framework exhibited notable activity comparable to a commercial Pt/C catalyst [84]. From the average values for alkaline (147 mV) and neutral (190 mV) environments, it can be concluded that the activity in an alkaline environment is still superior to a neutral one. However, the difference in overpotentials in both environments is not as significant as could be expected. The direct comparison suggests that great progress has been made in the development of HER catalysts for environmentally friendly water splitting at neutral pH.

Fig. 7. Comparison of overpotentials at 10 mA cm⁻² achieved by selected groups of cathode catalysts in alkaline media. 1 – outlying values, 2 – 90th percentile, 3 – 75th percentile, 4 – mean value, 5 – median, 6 – 25th percentile, 7 – 10th percentile.

Fig. 8. Comparison of overpotentials at 10 mA cm^{-2} achieved in alkaline and neutral media. 1 – outlying values, 2 – 90th percentile, 3 – 75th percentile, 4 – mean value, 5 – median, 6 – 25th percentile, 7 – 10th percentile.

6. Summary and outlook

Significant progress has been made in HER catalysis by non-precious metals and their alloys and compounds within recent years. The main parameters affecting the resulting catalytic activity can be summarised by the following points:

- (i) Favourable synergistic effects between various metals, groups or anion/cation relations,
- (ii) core/shell architecture of the designated catalyst,
- (iii) type of catalyst support with a high geometric area.

Pt-like catalytic activity has already been achieved for several Pt-free materials in an alkaline environment. Ni/Co-based alloys or phosphides doped with Fe and Mo seem to be the most promising alternatives to commercial platinum catalysts. Typically, these materials exhibit a high surface area and specific morphology with a high number of active sites. Moreover, the addition of Mo influences the energetics of water dissociation and M–H binding energy of the material, as well as the synergistic effect on the adjacent atoms.

The activity of the catalysts at neutral pH is gradually approaching the performance in an alkaline environment not only for Pt-based, but also for non-precious materials. Among the numerous possible materials, metal sulphides and phosphides seem to be the most promising ones considering their generally simple preparation, sufficient stability and activity toward the HER.

The most commonly reported electrocatalytic activity parameters, such as overpotential at a fixed current density (10 mA cm^{-2}) and Tafel slope, along with at least one of the classical stability tests were chosen as the main comparative parameters. For the sake of clarity, the comparison of the individual groups as well as of the most commonly used cations and cation-based materials were also presented in graphical form.

To ensure successful progress of research in this area in future, it is important to unify the testing protocol in order to allow a direct comparison of the different materials concerned. Many various electrocatalytic parameters can be found in the literature, but only a limited number can be used for a direct comparison of catalysts of varying particle sizes, morphology and topography. In addition, even fewer directly relevant for industrial application. Based on the available data, the presented review proposed a basic guideline for researchers to successfully fulfil these requirements.

Moreover, the simplicity of preparation, as well as possible scale-up for industrial application should be considered when developing new

cathode catalysts for alkaline water electrolysis. Last but not least, the price and abundance of the corresponding metals should also be taken into account as it will influence the overall costs.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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